

OUTSTANDING SCHOLARS WHO CONTRIBUTED A LOT TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEK TRANSLATION

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Abstract. *This article writes about outstanding Uzbek scientists who have made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek translation, about their scientific work, thanks to which we now easily make translations from one language to another correctly.*

Key words: *translation, ee-book, language, literature, scholar, the records, dictionary.*

ВЫДАЮЩИЕСЯ УЧЕНЫЕ, ВНЕСШИЕ БОЛЬШОЙ ВКЛАД В РАЗВИТИЕ УЗБЕКСКОГО ПЕРЕВОДА

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассказывается о выдающихся узбекских ученых, внесших большой вклад в развитие узбекского перевода, об их научной работе, благодаря которой мы теперь легко и правильно делаем переводы с одного языка на другой.*

Ключевые слова: *перевод, электронная книга, язык, литература, ученый, записи, словарь.*

Already in time immemorial, the Uzbek people, who've an ancient subculture, have been regarded in translation into their local language wonderful literary works of the East, they have become the belongings of way of life and records of Uzbekistan. The records of the Uzbek language are carefully related with translation. technological know-how and tradition. Literature changed into enriched with the aid of using translation with new motives, stories, artwork. That is why they have a look at of problems, associated with the records of the translation, will assist to repair particular paths improvement of Uzbek literature, its courting with literatures and lifestyle of different peoples. In his book, J.Sharipov included the records translation now no longer only works of art, however additionally philosophical, historical, geographical, medical, non-secular books, dictionaries, as nicely as diplomatic files and journalistic writings.

At monographs offer substances at the records of literature, stylistics, lexicology, dialectology. In a ee-book primarily based totally on a complete and cautious have a look at of archival documents, ee-book collections, periodical press, gives wealthy cloth on translations, made into Uzbek from Arabic, Persian for an extended duration of time, from the X century to the October revolution. The writer offers lots of latest statistics at the records dissemination of the Russian language and Russian literature in pre-innovative Turkestan, indicates the affect of superior thoughts Russian enlighteners. Recreating the records of the translation, J.Sharipov does now no longer tear it away from the records of the people. The precept of historicism is likewise maintained within side the feel that What J.Sharipov, From the records of translation to Uzbekistan.

Edited via way of means of G. Salyamov, "Science" UzSSR, Tashkent, 1965, 482 pages (in Uzbek). The writer believes: reading the records of translation activity, one cannot to technique the cloth of beyond eras from the factor of view of modern necessities for literary translations, however best taking into consideration the historical environment, stage of culture, literature and artwork with inside the beyond periods. Moreover, J. Sharipov does now no longer idealize the early translations, seeks to offer them a goal assessment. In the chapter "On pre-progressive translations from Russian into Uzbek language" consists of exciting authentic cloth.

As a result, after a protracted and cautious search, the writer controlled to locate 32 works Russian classical literature, translated at that point into Uzbek language. J.Sharipov collected, for example, pretty a lot famous and giant most of the Uzbek humans of fables and memories and, evaluating them with Krylov's fables, proved that this translations from Russian. A lot of labor has been executed to pick out the names of the primary translators with Russian into Uzbek.

It became now no longer smooth to clear up this trouble due to the fact that translators normally did now no longer provide their names, and this brought about confusion. So, for example, it turned into believed that "The Tale of the Fisherman and the Fish" Pushkin become translated via way of means of Furkat. Meanwhile, Furkat himself in the "Message Kokand poet Zakirjan Furkat from Istanbul" (1892) wrote: "I turned into very sorry that I did now no longer realize the Russian language, due to the fact as some distance as information of the Russian language is vital for scientists and merchants, so I want it for a touring person". Thanks to a protracted and painstaking search, J. Sharipov controlled to repair the names of the real translators of maximum of the works.

In particular, he accumulated exciting data approximately the Uzbek educator, translator of "Turkestan local newspaper" Sattarkhan, who knew Russian properly and promoted Russian tradition a number of the neighborhood population. The ee-book additionally contains records approximately the sports of predecessors and successors Sattarkhan - Shakhimardan Ibragimov, Hasan Chanyshhev, Sultana Isfandiyarov, Mullah Alime, Serykbay Okaev, Ali Askar Kalinen, Saidrasul Saidazizov, Gulamiddin Kabirzade, Ibrahim Davran and etc. The records of the interpretation exercise of the Uzbek humans starts offevolved with translations of Arabic and Persian books. Works translated from those languages, at one time enriched the treasury of our tradition, but lots of them had been undeservedly consigned to oblivion.

Most of ee-book "From the records of translation in Uzbekistan" is dedicated to the early period records of translation art. Names of eminent representatives home technological know-how and culture, together with Farabi, Avicenna, Biruni, Mahmud of Kashgar, Mahmud Zamakhshari, maximum in detail related to the interpretation records. In reference to their translation sports of J.Sharipov brightly illuminated the brand new factors of creativity those enlighteners. The ee-book indicates the sports of translators which include Qutb Khorezmi, Saif Saroi, Haydar Khorezmi, Alisher Navoi, Munis Khorezmi, analyzed the translations that belong to their pen.

In particular, the ee-book very well and punctiliously studied the works of Saadi "Guliston" (translator Saif Saroi), Firdowsi "Shah-name" (translator Khomushi), Nizami "Khosrov and Shirin" (translator Qutb Khorezmi). Highly treasured and comparisons of translations into Uzbek of "Kalila and Dimna", completed through translators Mulla Mukhamed Timur and Kara Fazlullah Almai. The author's statistics approximately the Khorezm faculty of translation, approximately the activities its representatives inclusive of Agakhi, Camille Khorezmi, Tabibi, Sanoi, Khabibi and so on.

The influence of these scholars on the development of Uzbek translation is enormous. Currently, new ways of using translation are being defined and implemented, and the mechanism of scientific research in this area is being improved.

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